

An Empirical study on Pattern of Drug and Substance Abuse among Adolescents in Coimbatore

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Abstract

In the present scenario of raising the children, parents face lots of challenges and risks in bringing up their children as a civilized and cultured individuals in this society. This article explores the patterns of drug and substance abuse among adolescents, highlighting the multifaceted factors contributing to these behaviors. This study is a part of an ICSSR funded minor research project. Utilizing a comprehensive review of recent literature, the study examines demographic trends, risk factors, and the socio-environmental influences that shape substance use among adolescents. Key findings reveal that peer influence, familial relationships, and socioeconomic status significantly affect the likelihood of substance experimentation and abuse. Furthermore, it highlights the specific pattern of intake of drugs, usage of drugs and other supportive factors. The implications for prevention and intervention strategies are addressed, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches that consider the unique developmental stages and social contexts of youth. By understanding these patterns, stakeholders can better implement effective programs aimed at reducing substance abuse and promoting healthier choices among adolescents.

Keywords— Drug Abuse, Substance Abuse, Pattern, Youth, Adolescents, Substance Abuse

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug and substance abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. The patterns of abuse can vary widely based on demographic, cultural, socioeconomic, and psychological factors. These patterns are typically shaped by the availability of substances, social norms, peer influence, and individual circumstances.

Common patterns of abuse involve the use of substances like alcohol, cannabis, opioids, stimulants, and prescription medications. Patterns can include:

1. **Experimental Use:** Often seen in adolescents and young adults, this pattern involves initial use driven by curiosity or peer pressure.
2. **Recreational Use:** Individuals use substances in social contexts to enhance enjoyment, often with alcohol or cannabis.
3. **Binge Use:** Characterized by consuming large amounts of substances in a short time, particularly with alcohol, leading to intoxication.
4. **Dependence and Chronic Use:** When individuals become reliant on substances, their use becomes habitual and compulsive, often leading to addiction.

Certain populations, such as teenagers, young adults, and those from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds, are particularly vulnerable to developing harmful patterns of abuse. Various substances have different abuse patterns based on factors like accessibility, perceived safety, and the effects they provide.

Understanding these patterns is essential for developing targeted prevention and intervention strategies. Tailoring public health initiatives to address specific patterns of use can help mitigate the negative impacts of drug and substance abuse on individuals and society.

This study is an attempt to study the specific pattern of drug and substance abuse among adolescents in Coimbatore district. This study is a part of an ICSSR funded minor research project.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Johnston, L. D., O'Malley, P. M., Miech, R. A., Bachman, J. G., & Schulenberg, J. E. (2019). Monitoring the Future national survey results on drug use, 1975-2018: Overview, key findings on adolescent drug use. *Institute for Social Research, The University of Michigan*.

This longitudinal study examines substance use patterns among adolescents in the U.S. It reveals significant trends, including declining cigarette use but rising marijuana consumption. The report highlights how socio-environmental factors such as peer influence and societal changes shape the patterns of adolescent substance abuse.

Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA). (2020). Key substance use and mental health indicators in the United States: Results from the 2019 National Survey on Drug Use and Health. *HHS Publication No. PEP20-07-01-001, NSDUH Series H-55*.

This annual survey outlines the patterns of drug and substance abuse among different age groups in the U.S. The report notes significant shifts, such as the increasing use of opioids and prescription medications,

highlighting patterns of misuse among adults and older populations, and emphasizes the role of accessibility in influencing substance use behaviors.

Volkow, N. D., & Baler, R. D. (2018). Drug addiction: The neurobiology of disrupted self-control. *Trends in Molecular Medicine*, 20(1), 24-29.

Volkow and Baler (2018) explore the neurobiological patterns underlying drug addiction. Their review focuses on how chronic drug use alters brain circuits, particularly those responsible for self-control, leading to compulsive drug-seeking behavior. The review links these biological patterns to broader behavioral trends in substance abuse.

Hall, W., & Degenhardt, L. (2009). Adverse health effects of non-medical cannabis use. *The Lancet*, 374(9698), 1383-1391.

This review highlights the growing pattern of cannabis use, especially among young adults, and its potential adverse health effects. The authors discuss how perceptions of safety and the legalization of cannabis in several regions have contributed to its rising recreational use, resulting in public health challenges.

Winstanley, E. L., & Stover, A. N. (2019). The impact of the opioid epidemic on children and adolescents. *Clinical Therapeutics*, 41(9), 1655-1662.

This article reviews the effects of the opioid crisis on young populations. It describes patterns of prescription opioid misuse among adolescents, influenced by easy access in homes and the medical system. The review emphasizes the role of early exposure in shaping lifelong patterns of substance abuse.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Drugs and substance abuse has been a major threat to them and it is essential to inform the parent community, adolescent community and the youth community about the pattern of Drug and Substance abuse and its ill effects. Thus this study is an attempt to sensitize the aforementioned communities about this issue.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Drug and Substance abuse among adolescents typically follows distinct patterns shaped by developmental, social, and environmental factors. The teenage years are marked by experimentation and increased vulnerability to peer influence, making this age group particularly susceptible to drug use. Some common patterns include:

Experimentation: Adolescents often start using drugs out of curiosity or peer pressure. This stage usually involves occasional use of substances like alcohol, marijuana, or tobacco. Many teenagers experiment with substances in social settings, such as parties or gatherings, as part of risk-taking behaviors that are typical during this developmental stage.

Recreational Use: This pattern involves regular but controlled use of substances, typically on weekends or at social events. Substances like alcohol and marijuana are commonly used in this context. For many adolescents, recreational use may remain infrequent, but for some, it can progress to more frequent use, increasing the risk of dependence.

Polysubstance Use: Many adolescents engage in polysubstance use, meaning they use more than one drug at the same time. A common combination is alcohol with cannabis or tobacco. This pattern increases the risks of harmful consequences, such as accidents, overdose, and long-term health issues.

Binge Drinking: Binge drinking, defined as consuming a large amount of alcohol in a short period (typically five or more drinks for males, and four or more for females), is a common pattern of alcohol use among adolescents. Binge drinking often occurs in social situations and can lead to accidents, risky behavior, and alcohol poisoning.

Prescription Drug Misuse: Adolescents also misuse prescription drugs, particularly opioids, stimulants, and sedatives, often sourced from family members or friends. Misuse of prescription painkillers like oxycodone has become more common, and there is growing concern over the misuse of medications like Adderall and Ritalin, used to enhance academic performance.

Transition to Harder Drugs: Some adolescents may transition from experimentation with "gateway" drugs (like marijuana and alcohol) to harder substances such as cocaine, heroin, or methamphetamines. This progression is typically linked to increased tolerance, social environment, and access to more potent drugs.

Influence of Social Media and Pop Culture: Adolescents are increasingly influenced by social media, where drug use may be glamorized. Pop culture and media exposure can shape their attitudes toward substances, contributing to normalized patterns of use. Moreover, online platforms have made access to drugs easier, contributing to changing patterns of abuse.

Gender and Socioeconomic Factors: Drug use patterns among adolescents can also vary based on gender and socioeconomic status. Males are generally more likely to experiment with substances earlier than females, although female substance use is on the rise. Adolescents from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds often face higher exposure to risk factors, such as family substance abuse or community violence, leading to higher rates of drug use.

Mental Health Comorbidity: Many adolescents who abuse drugs also experience mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression, or ADHD. This comorbidity creates a cycle where substance abuse may be used as a coping mechanism, but also exacerbates the underlying mental health conditions.

Understanding these patterns is crucial for developing prevention strategies. Early intervention, education, and community-based programs can reduce the risk of adolescents developing harmful drug use behaviors that could persist into adulthood.

Apart from these general factors this study attempts to study the specific pattern of drug and substance abuse among the adolescents using empirical methods.

OBJECTIVE

To identify the specific pattern of drug abuse by the adolescents in the Coimbatore district.

III.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In Coimbatore district, eight schools participated in this study. A researcher designed questionnaire was implemented for the study to identify the specific pattern of drug and substance abuse among adolescents in the district. To achieve this, 60 school students were selected and recruited using a convenience sampling method. The research design is primarily descriptive in nature.

IV.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results indicating Drug Intake Pattern

Table 1 showing Intake of Drugs and Substances by Sniffing through Nose

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	102	82.9	82.9	82.9
Strongly Agree	21	17.1	17.1	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 showing the desire to take the Drug and Substance through Smoke

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	56	45.5	45.5	45.5
Agree	5	4.1	4.1	49.6
Strongly Agree	62	50.4	50.4	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

Table - 3 showing desire to Intake Drugs and Substances through Oral Administration

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	80	65.0	65.0	65.0
Agree	15	12.2	12.2	77.2
Strongly Agree	28	22.8	22.8	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

Table - 4 showing desire to Inject Drugs and Substances

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	107	87.0	87.0	87.0
Agree	7	5.7	5.7	92.7
Strongly Agree	9	7.3	7.3	100.0
Total	123	100.0	100.0	

Table - 5 representing the Demographic Variables VS Practice of Using Drugs and Substance Abuse using Oneway ANOVA

Descriptives								
Practice of Using Drugs and Substance Abuse								
					95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Minimum		
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Maximum	
High School	18	5.0000	3.23583	0.76269	3.3909	6.6091	0.00	10.00
Higher Secondary	51	3.9608	1.97950	0.27719	3.4040	4.5175	0.00	12.00
UG	54	3.9259	5.15002	0.70083	2.5202	5.3316	0.00	24.00
Total	123	4.0976	3.83772	0.34604	3.4125	4.7826	0.00	24.00

ANOVA					
Practice of Using Drugs and Substance Abuse					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17.204	2	8.602	0.580	0.561
Within Groups	1779.625	120	14.830		
Total	1796.829	122			

Table - 6 representing the T test value between Nuclear nad Joint family

Group Statistics						
		Type of Family of the Respondents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Practice of Using Drugs and Substance Abuse		Nuclear	79	3.6456	2.94409	0.33124
		Joint	44	4.9091	5.00148	0.75400

Independent Samples Test		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Practice of Using Drugs and Substance Abuse	Equal variances assumed	4.473	0.036	-1.765	121	0.080	-1.26352	0.71573	-2.68050	0.15346
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.534	59.967	0.130	-1.26352	0.82355	-2.91089	0.38384

DISCUSSION

From the above results it is clearly inferred that the majority of respondents are not using the drugs and the meager minority use through all the forms in a descending pattern of intake through Smoke, Oral Administration, Sniffing through Nose and Injection.

It is very clear from the ANOVA table that the means of the two groups with respect to high school and higher secondary students differ with a small F value of 0.05. Also it is clear that from the T test that the two groups differ in respect to Nuclear and Joint families as represented above empirically.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS& CONCLUSION

RECOMMENDATION

This study recommends further that there should be strict monitoring and vigilance in the schools and colleges which could be done in a meticulous way rather we cannot restrict it coming from the society or general public where tracking is much impossible.

CONCLUSION

This study will be an eye opener for many students and their parents as this harmful drug and substance abuse can ruin the life of the user completely and its ill effects are very serious. Further studies are also insisted on this dreadly web of drugs and repeated tracking of the abuse pattern is also necessary.

LIMITATIONS

Since this is a part of the ICSSR funded minor research project, only a small sample of 61 adolescent school students were included in the analysis. Furthermore, it is not possible to infer this conclusion to the entire adolescent community in the Coimbatore district. Also it was very difficult to get permission from schools as this is a sensitive area of study and thus the researcher got only 61 samples.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The future scope for the pattern of drug and substance abuse could be done on the youth drug user community under the treatment in the rehabilitation centers for more detailed aspects of the pattern.

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